

Banzaï Biostimulant: Plant Defense Stimulator (PDS) of cocoa trees in the fight against *Phytophthora* sp.?

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Abstract

Cocoa cultivation represents the most important socio-economic asset of the state of Côte d'Ivoire. However, it is subject to many constraints such as land scarcity, harmful action of pests and diseases. To overcome this state of affairs, a new range of biological inputs has intervened on the agricultural market; these are biostimulants and / or plant defense stimulator. The objective of this work was to evaluate the effectiveness of the biostimulant Banzaï against brown rot giving it the status of defense stimulator. The experimental device, repeated three times, is composed of a Fischer block composed of six randomized plots noted T01, T02, T1, T2, T3 and T4 each composed of twenty cocoa trees tests highlighting three or four applications of the biostimulant with or without fertilizer input. The results obtained showed that the plots treated with the banzaï biostimulant controlled the rot of the cherries better than the control plots ($p < 0.05$). However, for pod rot, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was recorded, although at the descriptive level the control plots had the highest rot rates. As for the treatments, the T4 treatment (four applications of Banzaï with fertilizer input) is the one that best controlled the brown rot of cherries and pods. However, to consider the biostimulant Banzaï as a defense stimulator in its own right a more in-depth study on the durability of the protective action against *Phytophthora* sp is indispensable.

Keywords: Cocoa, *Phytophthora* sp, Plant Defense Stimulator, Ivory Coast.

INTRODUCTION

As the world's largest cocoa producer, Côte d'Ivoire produced 2,000,000 tons of cocoa beans in 2018, or 40% of the world's supply (BCEAO, 2014; World Bank, 2019). Cocoa cultivation represents the most important socio-economic asset of the state of Côte d'Ivoire with 15% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and 30% of export earnings (Assiri et al., 2015; Koua et al., 2018; ICCO, 2018).

Despite these socio-economic advantages, cocoa cultivation in Côte d'Ivoire is subject to many constraints including the aging of cocoa orchards, the instability of cocoa purchase prices, pest attacks, Swollen shoot disease and also the brown rot of pods (Freud et al., 2000, Oro et al., 2020A, Oro et al., 2020b).

In Ivorian orchards, brown pod rot due to *Phytophthora* spp causes significant damage (Figure 1) of the order of 44% crop losses (Koua et al., 2018). In the most disease-friendly areas, losses can reach 80% of the crop (Koua et al., 2018). Four species of *Phytophthora* are responsible for the disease of brown pod rot in Côte d'Ivoire. Of these four species, two are commonly found in Ivorian cocoa farms. These are *Phytophthora palmivora* which is the most widespread species, and *Phytophthora megakarya*, apparently which is the least widespread but most aggressive species (Coulibaly et al, 2013).

To combat these pests, the majority of Ivorian farmers use pesticides, chemical fertilizers and synthetic fungicides. However, their uses affect non-target organisms, in particular earthworms and soil microbiota,

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and soil quality by degrading its physicochemical composition (Eijsackers et al., 2005; Karas et al., 2018; Amossé et al., 2020). In addition, the use of these chemically synthetic products has a negative impact on the health of the population and its environment in the long term (Okoffo et al., 2017; Ano et al., 2018; Affum et al., 2018).

The harmful action of these synthetic products on the microbiota, soil quality, the environment and on the health of populations has strongly encouraged the search for alternative biological solutions to improve plant yields but also their protection against pests, pathogens and various diseases (Olanrewaju et al., 2017; Batool and Iqbal, 2019). Thus, in recent years, a new category of products and substances has developed within the market of agricultural inputs; these are biostimulants and plant defense stimulators (PDS).

Biostimulants, consisting of microalgae, fungi and other forms of products of plant and/or biological origin, affect the ability of systems to adapt to attacks by bio-aggressors or problems with the availability of nutrients by stimulating both crop yields and the vigor of flowers and fruits against external diseases and stresses (EBIC, 2014; Oro et al., 2020C; Dekhordi et al., 2021).

Similarly, plant defense stimulators, or PDS, represent a new generation of phytosanitary inputs intended not to directly destroy bio-aggressors but to force crops to activate their own immune system to reduce their susceptibility to biotic diseases and stresses, unlike biostimulants which are approved as fertilizers (Walters et al., 2013 ; Gaucher et al., 2020).

The general objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of the banzaï biostimulant in the biocontrol of brown rot of cherries and pods giving it the status of stimulator of natural defense of cocoa plants against rot disease. Specifically, it will be about of comparing the effect of the three and four applications of Banzaï associated with the contribution of fertilizers being tested in the control of cherries and pod rot.

Figure 1: Visible symptoms of brown rot of cocoa pods in a peasant plantation in Côte d'Ivoire (Photo taken by Yapi Xavier)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study site

This study was carried out on three sites in the sub-prefecture of Moronou in the department of Toumodi. With an area of about 2,837 km², this department of high cocoa production estimated at nearly 9,000 tons per year is located 198 km from Abidjan, the economic capital and 34 km from Yamoussoukro, the political and administrative capital of Côte d'Ivoire (AIP, 2013).

Equipment

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The plant material consisted of Forastero-type cocoa trees at least 10 years old in peasant plantations. The technical equipment used are: the banzaï test product; the fertilizers adopted for cocoa production; an atomizer to apply the Banzaï biostimulant on cocoa trees; a decameter to delimit the experimental blocks; ribbons and paints to mark trees, cherries and newly produced or rotten pods.

Banzaï biostimulant

According to the firm Callivoire (2017), Banzaï, is a biostimulant specific to the fruiting of cocoa that increases the yield of cocoa trees. It promotes flowering, limits the fall of flowers and cherries. It stimulates the vigor of the pods against diseases and external stresses. Banzaï is an innovative patented technology that comes in the form of two formulations, including Banzaï 1, packaged in a white package and Banzaï 2, in a yellow packaging (Figure 2). These two formulations are previously mixed before application. The optimal treatment requires four applications at the interval of one month from the first rains, that is, between April and September. This period of application indicated corresponds to the appearance of the first flowers (CNRA, 2009).

Figure 2: Banzaï biostimulant

Methods

Experimental arrangement

The experimental device is composed of a Fischer block composed of six randomized plots noted T01, T02, T1, T2, T3 and T4 each composed of twenty feet tests of cocoa trees. The experimental device is repeated at three sites. The different plots are composed as follows:

- T01 represents the witness without application of Banzaï but with a contribution of fertilizer.
- T02 represents the control without application of Banzaï without fertilizer input.
- T1 is a plot that has received three applications of Banzaï with a fertilizer input.
- T2 is a plot that has received four applications of Banzaï without fertilizer input.
- T3 is a plot that has received three applications of Banzaï without fertilizer input
- T4 is a plot that has received four applications of Banzaï with fertilizer input.

Observation and data collection

The observations were made along the test cocoa trees in the range of 0 to 2.35 m from ground level every two weeks for nine months, i.e. from July to February. Data collection focused on four variables: the number of cherries produced, the number of rotten cherries, the number of pods produced, and the number of rotten pods. The cherries is an immature pod less than six centimeters in size while, the pod is larger than six centimeters in length. The counting of cherries and pods was cumulative between two observations. During

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each observation, the cherries and pods, healthy as rotten, were tied to their peduncle by a colored string to distinguish them from the new cherries and pods produced at the next sighting.

Data analysis

The data collected on the card and entered in the Excel Spreadsheet were analyzed using the IBM SPSS 20.0 statistical software. The first step was to describe the dynamics of evolution of the rate of rot of cherries and pods (Equation 1) per month of observation according to treatments. Then, in a second step, it was a question of comparing the average rates of rot per treatment. In case of significant statistical difference, a classification was made to prioritize the different treatments according to their effectiveness in the biocontrol of brown rot of pods and cherries. The statistical test used for this rate comparison was the Kruskal-Wallis test, a non-parametric alternative to the ANOVA test to a factor in case of non-normality of distributions.

$$\text{Equation (1): Rate of rot} = \frac{NCI * 100}{ASC}$$

NCI = Number of pods/cherries attacked by rot

ASC = Number of pods/cherries produced.

RESULTS

Effect of biostimulant and fertiliser on the biocontrol of cherries rot

Figure 3 shows the dynamics of evolution of the rate of rotten cherries per treatment and per month of observation. It shows rot peaks for all plots during the September-October and January-February periods. This dynamic of evolution shows overall a higher rate of rotten cherries in the control plots T01 and T02. Plot T01 is the one that has the highest rate over practically the entire duration of the observation and reaches its maximums during the months of September to October with rates exceeding 50% of rotten cherries. The treated plots, however, have rot rates of the order of 20% to 25% and generally lower than those of the control plots. For the treated plots, Figure 3 also shows that plots T2 (four applications of Banzaï without fertilizer) and T4 (four applications of Banzaï with fertilizer) have the lowest rates of cherries rot over the entire observation.

Figure 3: Dynamics of the evolution of the rate of cherries rot by treatment according to the months of observation

The following Figure 4 shows the mustache boxes of rotten cherries rates per treatment and the result of the comparison analysis of cherries rot rates per treatment. The Kruskal-Wallis test result ($p=0.000 < 0.05$) showed a significant difference in the rates of rotten cherries per treatment. The classification of treatments according to their effectiveness (Table 1) in the biocontrol of cherries rot showed four distinct classes. Class

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A, which is represented by the T4 treatments (four applications of Banzaï with fertilizer input) and T2 (four applications of Banzaï without fertilizer input), is the one that has been the most effective in the control of cherries rot. It is followed by class AB which contains exclusively the T02 tell-tale with intermediate efficiency. Then class B, which is represented by the treatments T1 (three applications of Banzaï with fertilizer input) and T3 (three applications of Banzaï without fertilizer input) with a lower efficiency than that of class B. Finally, class D, which is the class of low efficiency in the control of cherries rot with exclusively the T01 control.

Figure 4: Boxpots of the rate of rot of cherries produced by treatment.

The significant difference between the treatments and the control shows that the biostimulant had a positive effect in controlling cherries rot. However, plots treated with four applications of the banzaï biostimulant better controlled the brown rot of cherries with rates between 16 and 18% (Table 1). However, the three applications of Banzaï have been of no contribution in the fight against brown cherries rot. Similarly, the contribution of fertilizer during the experiment also had no influence on the control of brown cherries rot.

Table 1: Prioritization of treatments according to their effectiveness in the biocontrol of cherries rot

Treatments	Average rot rates	Classifications
T4	15,87%	A
T2	17,87%	A
T02	20,54%	AB
T3	20,84	B
T1	21,48%	B
T01	26,81%	C

Effect of biostimulant and fertiliser on the biocontrol of pod rot

Figure 5 shows the dynamics of evolution of the rate of rotten pods per treatment over the nine months of observation. This dynamic of evolution shows for all treatments a peak in the rate of rotten pods in the month of October. In this period the control plots T01 and T02 had the highest rates of rotten pods which reached 40% and 30% respectively. In general, these two plots had obtained higher rates than those of the plots treated with the banzaï biostimulant.

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Figure 5: Dynamics of the evolution of the rate of pod rot by treatment according to the months of observation

Figure 6: Boxplots of pod rot rate per treatment.

Figure 6 shows the boxplots of the rate of rotten pods by treatment and the result of the comparative analysis of rot rates. It shows that treated plots have boxes and lengths of whiskers that are shorter and closer to 0% than control plots. Nevertheless, the comparative analysis did not show a significant difference. Although there is no significant difference between treatments, descriptive analysis (Table 2) showed that control plots had higher average rates of rotten pods than control plots.

Table 2: Average Pod Rot Rates by Treatment

Treatments	Average rot rates
T01	9,74%
T02	9,12%
T1	7,58%
T2	6,12%
T3	7,33%
T4	7,86%

4. DISCUSSION

The dynamics of evolution of the rate of cherries and rotten pods by treatment and by observation period showed that rot peaks appeared in the period from September to October for all treatments. These peaks correspond to the post-period of high production of cherries and pods which occurs respectively two months and three months after the strong rainy season that takes place each year during the months of April-May-June (CNRA, 2009). This result is in line with that presented by Oro and his collaborators who found a pod rot rate of around 48% in the month of October in their study on brown pod rot on a site in the department of Toumodi (Oro et al., 2020A). It is also in accordance with the results obtained by these same authors (Oro et al., 2020D) on the rot of cherries which had for all plots combined reached the highest average rate of rot in October at 47% in the same department.

Comparison of cherries rot rates between treatments showed that plots treated with Banzai biostimulant had a better effect in controlling cherries rot than control plots. Indeed, control plots T01 and T02, which did not receive the application of Banzai biostimulant, were subjected to a stronger parasitic pressure related to the pathogen *Phytophthora spp* of brown rot (Kébé et al., 2009). This is in line with Callivoire (2017) whose biostimulant Banzai promotes flowering, limits the fall of flowers and cherries by allowing it to better resist stress and diseases.

In addition, the three applications of Banzai showed less effectiveness in controlling cherries rot than the four applications of the biostimulant. Indeed, Callivoire (2017) and Oro and his collaborators (2020A, 2020B, 2020C and 2020D) have shown that the four applications of Banzai applied monthly over four months stimulate the production of cherries and pods while stimulating their vigor against attacks and pathogens.

However, the result of the comparative analysis in the context of the control of brown pod rot showed no significant difference. This explains why the effect of the biostimulant in controlling pod rot is not clearly established as shown by Oro and his collaborators on brown pod rot (Oro et al., 2020D). Nevertheless, in descriptive terms, the control plots experienced higher rates of pod rot than those of the treated plots. This could suggest that the four applications needed to confer antifungal ability to cherries are not sufficient to confer it on pods that are produced later than cherries. The application of the biostimulant for its action on the already known productivity of four monthly applications over four months could therefore be insufficient than that necessary for the fight against brown pod rot. Thus, Marc Badin (2018) in his study on the protection of crops against diseases using microorganisms clearly established that the major challenges to be met for research with regard to biocontrol agents are in particular the knowledge of their biology, the effectiveness factors acting, their mechanisms of action and especially the consideration of the sustainability of the effectiveness of their protection. In the measure of this challenge, Gaucher and his collaborators in a recent study (2020) on the evaluation and optimization of the use of plant defense stimulators (PDS) in phytosanitary protection strategies in apple orchards showed that their effect persists only in the organs present at the time of treatment. This may explain why the action of the banzai biostimulant was more persistent on cherries than on pods produced later than cherries.

5. CONCLUSION

At the end of this study, it appears that the banzai biostimulant was effective in controlling cherries rot unlike pod rot where the differences observed between the controls and the treated plots were not significant. As for the treatments, the T4 treatment (four applications of Banzai with fertilizer input) is the one that best controlled the brown rot of cherries and pods. However, to consider the banzai biostimulant as a defense stimulator in its own right, a more in-depth study on a prolonged application of this biostimulant will make it possible to definitively decide on the involvement of this biostimulant in the biocontrol of brown pod rot.

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BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- i Affum OA, Acquah SO, Osae SD. and Kwaansa-Ansah EE: 2018. Distribution and risk assessment of banned and other current-use pesticides in surface and groundwaters consumed in an agricultural catchment dominated by cocoa crops in the Ankobra Basin, Ghana. *Science of the Total Environment*. Volume 633. Pages 630-640.
- ii Agence Ivoirienne de Presse (AIP): 2013. Monograph of the department of Toumodi. Abidjan.Net. Visit date: 22/12/2018. 5p.
- iii Amossé J, Bart S, Brulle F, Tebby C, Beaudouin R, Néliou S, Lamy I, Péry ARR. and Pelosi C: 2020. A two years field experiment to assess the impact of two fungicides on earthworm communities and their recovery. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 203:110979.
- iv Ano EJ, Tahiri A, Diby YKS. and Siapo YM: 2018. Evaluation of peasant phytosanitary practices in cocoa farms: Case of the department of Abengourou (East, Côte d'Ivoire). *Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences*, Vol. 38, Issue 1: 6159-6174.
- v Assiri AA, Konan A, N'Guessan KF, Kébé BI, Kassin KE, Coulibaly JY, Yapo AR, Yoro GR. and Yao-Kouamé A: 2015. Comparison of two cocoa replanting techniques on a non-forest cropping background in Côte d'Ivoire. *African Crop Science Journal*, 23, No. 4, pp. 365-378.
- vi Central Bank of West African States (BCEAO): 2014. Monographic study on the cocoa sector in the WAEMU, 33 Pages.
- vii World Bank: 2019. "In the land of cocoa how to transform Ivory Coast." World Bank, NW Washington, DC.
- viii Bardin M: 2018. Protection of crops against diseases with the help of microorganisms: state of the art and perspectives. *Med'agri*, Avignon, France. 34 pp. fhal-01974613.
- ix Batool S. and Iqbal A: 2019. Phosphate solubilizing rhizobacteria as alternative of chemical fertilizer for growth and yield of *Triticum aestivum*. *Saudi J Biol Sci*. 26 (7) :1400-1410.
- x Callivoire: 2017. Banzai biostimulant. Callivoire report. p-2.
- xi Centre National de Recherche Agronomique (CNRA): 2009. Growing cocoa well in Côte d'Ivoire. Cocoa technical sheet. pp. 1-4.
- xii Coulibaly KK, IB Kebe, Koffi NK, Mpika J. and Kone D: 2013. Characterization of *Phytophthora* spp isolates from the cocoa orchard of Cote D'Ivoire. *Journal of Applied Biosciences* 70:5567-5579.13-14p.
- xiii Dehkordi AR, Roghani RS. and Asghari B: 2021. Effects of biostimulants on morpho-physiological traits of various ecotypes of fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.) under water deficit stress. *Scientia horticultrae*. Volume 283. 110077.
- xiv Eijsackers H, Beneke P, Maboeta M, Louw JPE. And Reinecke AJ: 2005. The implications of copper fungicide usage in vineyards for earthworm activity and resulting sustainable soil quality. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 62(1):99-111.
- xv European biostimulants industry council (EBIC): 2014. Promoting the biostimulant industry and the rule of plant biostimulants in making agriculture more sustainable. (<http://www.biostimulants.eu/>).
- xvi Freud EH, Petithuguenin P. and Richard J: 2000. Cocoa fields: a challenge for competitiveness in Africa Asia. Editions Karthala and CIRAD, Paris, France, 207 p.
- xvii Gaucher M, Lemarquand A, Orain G, Giraud M, Le Maguet J, Coureau C, Leblois A, Belleveaux C, Cavaignac S, Biargues ME, Koké E, Bérud M, Crété X, Ondet SJ, Meynard J. and Brisset MN: 2020. PEPS: Evaluation and optimization of the use of plant defense stimulators (SDP) in phytosanitary protection strategies in apple orchards. *Agronomic Innovations*.79, 159-171.
- xviii International Cocoa Council Organization (ICCO): 2018. Quarterly Bulletin of Cocoa Statistics. Vol. XLIV, No. 3, Cocoa year 2017/18.
- xix Karas PA, Baguelin C, Pertile G, Papadopoulou ES, Nikolaki S, Storck V, Ferrari F, Trevisan M, Ferrarini A, Fornasier F, Vasileiadis S, Tsiamis G, Martin-Laurent F. and Karpouzias DG: 2018.

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Assessment of the impact of three pesticides on microbial dynamics and functions in a lab-to-field experimental approach, Sci Total Environ. 637-638 :636-646.

- xx Kébé BI, Joseph M, Kouamé FN, Prakash KH, Gary SS. and AKE S: 2009. Isolation and identification of indigenous cocoa microorganisms in Côte d'Ivoire and highlighting their antagonistic effects vis-à-vis *Phytophthora palmivora*, agent of brown pod rot. *Science & Nature*, 6 (1), 71-82.
- xxi Koua S H, Coulibaly NA M-D. and Alloueboraud WAM: 2018. Characterization of orchards and cocoa diseases in Côte d'Ivoire: case of the departments of Abengourou, Divo and Soubré. *Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 35, (3): 5706-5714p.
- xxii Koua S, Coulibaly N. and Allocated B: 2018. Characterization of orchards and cocoa diseases in Côte d'Ivoire: case of the departments of Abengourou, Divo and Soubré. *Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*. Vol.35, Issue 3: 5706-5714.
- xxiii Okoffo ED, Fosu-Mensah BY. And Gordon C: 2017. Contamination levels of organophosphorus and synthetic pyrethroid pesticides in cocoa beans from Ghana, *Food Control*, Volume 73, Part B, Pages 1371-1378.
- xxiv Olanrewaju OS, Glick BR. and Babalola OO: 2017. Mechanisms of action of plant growth promoting bacteria. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol*. 33 (11) :197. (2017).
- xxv Oro FZ, Lallie H-D, Brou GK, Bi-Zaouli P, Fofana JI. and Diallo HA: 2020C. Efficacy of Banzai TM Biostimulant on improving the leaf cover of apparently healthy cocoa trees and cocoa trees with "Swollen shoot" disease in Petit Bondoukou, South-West Côte d'Ivoire. *Journal of Applied Biosciences*. 146 : 15064-15073.
- xxvi Oro FZ, Lallie H-D, Kouamé GF, Sanouidi D. and Diallo HA: 2020. Evaluation of the biostimulant Banzai's effect and the previous fertilizer on the control of cocoa black cherries disease in N'Gouaminkro, in the department of Toumodi, Côte d'Ivoire. *World Journal of Agricultural Research*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 62-69.
- xxvii Oro FZ, Lallie H-D, N'Guessan CA, Kouadio J, Diby L, Kouamé C. and Diallo HA: 2020B. Effect of Proper Management of Cocoa Plants on the Occurrence of Swollen Shoot Disease in Kipiri - Côte d'Ivoire. *Journal of Experimental Agriculture International*. 42 (3): 159-166.
- xxviii Oro FZ, Lallie H-D, Silué S, Sanouidi D. and Diallo HA: 2020A. Comparison of the effect of banzai biostimulant and fertilizer on cocoa pod rot in the department of Toumodi, Centre-Est of Côte d'Ivoire. *Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences (JAPS)*. Volume 45, Number 1, page 7822-7838.
- xxix Walters DR, Ratsep J. and Havis ND: 2013. Controlling crop diseases using induced resistance: challenges for the future. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 64, 1263–1280.